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Teacher Education, Professional Development and the Implication of Modern Day Slavery in Education in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined teacher education, professional development and the implication of modern day slavery in education in Delta State, Nigeria. The investigation is premised on the fact that adequate and appropriate teacher education is capable of resisting modern day slavery in the teaching profession. The paper was guided by some objectives. The design of the study is the descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised teachers of public and private secondary schools in the state. The study randomly selected 318 participants, that is, 106 respondents each from the three senatorial districts of the state. The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. The instrument was rated on a 4 point moderated scale of strongly agree =4, agree =3, disagree =2 and strongly disagree =1. Data generated was analyzed using mean ($\bar{x}$) and standard deviation statistics at a benchmark of $p \leq 2.50$ as region for rejection and $p \geq 2.50$ as region for acceptance of the research question. Findings revealed that adequate and appropriate teacher education and professional development is capable of eradicating modern day slavery in the teaching profession. The paper concludes that, adequate and appropriate teacher education and professional development places the teacher in a better position to identify and resist modern day slavery in the profession. The paper recommended that in the cause of training teachers, adequate and appropriate knowledge should be imbued in them so that they will recognize when slavery tenet in being applied to their duties and responsibilities as a teacher.

Keywords: Teacher, Teacher Education, Professional Development, Modern Day Slavery.

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Introduction

A teacher is a person that indoctrinates others for the purpose of achieving a desire skill or expertise as the case may. A teacher is a person that oversee training in an informal or a formal setting depending on the scope of the training being undertaken. A teacher in the formal setting has to do with teaching in the regulation setting, usually called a school where students are present to be taught by a teacher while a teacher in an informal setting has to do with teaching and training of pupils and children at home or in an uncoordinated setting. In whatever capacity and style the training takes, it is pertinent to state that, it is being undertaken by a person who is more vast in knowledge than the trainee or students. This training and teaching is not done at random, it is done within a specific time frame, usually for a reward, either financially or in kind or for the sake of motivation, hence, the teacher that undertakes such are expected to be given a form of gratification, that is usually agreed upon and thus, any deviation from the said agreement amounts to a breach of agreement and in most cases, litigation is undertaken to redress the injustice. Instances abound where such disagreement arises, and the teacher in question cannot leave or seek litigation as a result of him being threatened one way or the other. Hence the teacher is mandated or forced to work without compensation or the scope of the contract of teaching extended without relevant and accompanying compensations, thus leading to a forced labour in the profession in a modern setting (Cole, 2007). Teachers in the present times, especially those in private institutions are made to undertake teaching that is not part of their scope of employment. They are being threatened with dismissal and coerced into doing what they were not employed for just to please their employer. They undertake extra studies and undertake tasks outside the school context. These extra tasks are sometimes not paid for and even when they are paid for, it is a peanut compared to the task done within that time. Teachers on their part undertake the task simply because they fear the repercussion and consequences of them acting otherwise; knowing fully well the nature of things in the country with its attendant bad and perilous economic situation and lack of gainful employment and jobs, so risking what they have by means of rejecting assigned job, is a risk they are not willing to take, thus, employers capitalizes on it to compel teachers to undertake rigorous teaching and task outside the context of their employment./ Furthermore, teachers are forced to teach, in most cases virtually all students in the school because of lack of teachers in various subject areas in the school (Williamson-McDiarmid and Clevenger-Bright, 2008). The implication here is that teachers are labored above what they bargained for when they accept the employment to teach in the particular school. This view gave impetus to the need for adequate teacher education so that they know their 'onion' and can withstand pressure arising from their professional engagement.

Teacher education according to Goods Dictionary of Education (2013) means, all the formal and non-formal activities and experiences that help to qualify a person to assume responsibilities of a member of the educational profession or to discharge his responsibilities more effectively. In the past, the programme of teacher preparation was called teacher training. It prepared teachers as mechanics or technicians. It had narrower goals with its focus being only on skill training. The perspective of teacher education was therefore very narrow and its scope was limited. As McNergney and Herbert (2001) put it, "training is given to

animals and circus performers, while education is to human beings”. It is pertinent to note that, teacher education encompasses teaching skills, sound pedagogical theory and professional skills which makes a complete teacher in the teaching profession.

Professional development entails a situation whereby a teacher undertake or undergo training outside its teacher training in order for him to acquire additional skills that will be beneficial in the teaching learning process. Professional development of teachers comes in the form of them acquiring skills via seminars, workshops, mentoring and peer observation, informal dialogue to improve teaching, amongst others. The acquisition of these additional training stands the teacher in good stead to deliver effectively on his or her subject matter (OECD, 2005). The implication here is that professional development of a teacher enhances the teacher’s capability to pass across subject content to students without any fear or intimidation. Furthermore, professional development of the teacher is essential because of the onerous task they face from school owners and school heads. They are asked to teach in increasingly multicultural classrooms; to place greater emphasis on integrating students with special learning needs in their classrooms; to make more effective use of information and communication technologies for teaching; to engage more in planning within evaluative and accountability frameworks; to undertake task outside their professional delineation and to do more to involve parents in schools’ affair. These duties assigned to the teacher goes way beyond the terms of their employment, hence the presence of exploitation on the teacher. Teacher education and professional development are two side of a coin, one complements the other in a bid to actualize educational objectives in the school setting. In the light of the above, the study examines teacher education, professional development and the implication for modern day slavery in Delta State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Teacher education is regarded as a pre-service training of teachers while professional development is an in-service one where the teacher strives to improve upon his or her acquired knowledge in a bid to deliver on subject content effectively for students comprehension. In the light of this, teacher education and professional development is suppose to be seamless but the presence of victimization, discrimination and other negative vices experienced and witnessed in the profession have tended to erode the zeal and desire the profession accords in the eye of practitioners and would-be teachers in the state. the low level of motivation – working without regular wages as at when due and wages below the minimum national standard and high level of coercion and discrimination and in some cases contract slavery necessitated the need to have rethink on how the profession is being coordinated. Against this backdrop, this study looks at teacher education, professional development and the implication of modern day slavery in education in Delta State, Nigeria with a bid to proffering solution on how modern day slavery could be eradicated from the profession.

Research Question

- i. To what extent would adequate and appropriate teacher education and professional development eliminate modern day slavery in the teaching profession?

Teacher Education and Modern Day Slavery

Teacher education entails a situation whereby teachers are indoctrinated on the nitty-gritty of the teaching profession. Teacher education in the view of Sanyal (2013), teacher education entails the policies and procedures designed to equip prospective teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school and wider community. Although ideally it should be conceived of, and organized as a seamless continuum, teacher education is often divided into these stages, viz-a-viz; initial teacher training / education (a pre-service course before entering the classroom as a fully responsible teacher); induction (the process of providing training and support during the first few years of teaching or the first year in a particular school); and teacher development or continuing professional development (CPD) (an in-service process or practicing teacher) (Sanyal, 2013). Teacher education in the view of The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) (1998) is the programme of education, research and training of persons to teach from pre-primary to higher education level. Implicit here is that teacher education empowers a person to teach all categories of students. Furthermore, Arora (2002) stated that, “teacher education is a programme that is related to the development of teacher proficiency and competence that would enable and empower the teacher to meet the requirements of the profession and face the challenges therein”. Emphasis here is placed on the overall development of the teacher to meet students needs in the teaching learning process. Also, teacher education is undertaken to groom the teacher to undertake task that is related to his or her area of study; but in the real world, teachers are made to undertake task outside their professional competence in a bid by the employer to cut cost. Cutting of cost here implies a situation whereby the employer jettisons the hiring of subject teacher to avoid incurring extra cost. The implication here is that, when such situation occur, it is the teacher already have that bears the brunt of the labour to augment for the shortfall in staff strength; hence teacher being forced to teach what they did not learn at the teacher training institution (Chaurasia, 2000).

Learning to become a professional teacher is achieved through teacher education. Conceptually, the term teacher education in the context of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 6th edition (2013) in her National Policy on Education is the type of education received at tertiary education given after secondary education in universities, colleges of education, polytechnic, monotechnics including those institutions offering correspondence courses. According to Osuji (2009), teacher education refers to professional education of teachers towards attainment of attitudes, skills and knowledge considered desirable so as to make them efficient and effective in their work in accordance with needs of a society at any point in time. It includes training/education occurring before commencement of service (pre-service) and education/training during service (in-service or on-the-job). As a matter of fact,

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teacher education is an organized training programme consisting both formal and non-formal education for the purpose of providing the school system with qualified, competent and professional teachers.

Teacher Professional Development and Modern Day Slavery

No matter how good pre-service training for teachers is, it cannot be expected to prepare teachers for all the challenges they will face throughout their careers. Education systems therefore seek to provide teachers with opportunities for in-service professional development in order to maintain a high standard of teaching and to retain a high-quality teacher workforce. As OECD's comparative review on teachers noted (OECD, 2005), "effective professional development is on-going, includes training, practice and feedback, and provides adequate time and follow-up support. Successful programmes involve teachers in learning activities that are similar to ones they will use with their students, and encourage the development of teachers' learning communities. There is growing interest in developing schools as learning organisations, and in ways for teachers to share their expertise and experience more systematically".

Modern day slavery manifests itself in a more institutionalized form that makes it difficult to be identified in the various areas of the state, including teacher education and training. Slavery in this context depicts a situation whereby a teacher is mandated to teach what he or she is not trained for without extra compensation from the authority responsible for teacher education and recruitment. Slavery in this context is most championed by educational authority, school administrators, amongst others in the educational institution. They tend to legitimize it by giving it a legal name of 'service to humanity', hence, it is not being perceived as slavery. In essence, teacher education that is meant to train a teacher in a specialized area of discipline for professionalism sake is being jettisoned for selfish reasons and greed on the part of authority. This is because, reasons adduced for mandating teachers to delve into other areas other than the area they were trained was on the ground of lack of financial resources for compensation, which they the authority have diverted for selfish reasons and others best known to them. This view was given impetus by the observation of ILO (2009), where they stated that educational authorities resolve to indulge in self-satisfaction and greed in the educational setting is the motivation for indulgence in educational slavery and unfair compensation to workers in the sector. They went further to state that such way of managing institution will inevitably lead to slavery in the administration of teacher and professional education and ultimately a fall in educational standard. Implicit here is that educational authority method is a tenacity to drift to slavery

Ways in Modern Day Slavery Manifest in the Teaching Profession

Slavery in the opinion of Kevin (2004) is a situation in which a person is owned or controlled by an employer, forced to work under an unhealthy condition, dehumanised and physically constrained. Modern day slavery in the teaching profession manifest in a diverse way from school authority controlling and increasing work load on teachers to authority forcing teachers to teach subject and students outside their scope of employment, to dehumanization and physically constraining teachers from professional development that will

enhance their teaching proficiency for selfish and sinister reasons. It is pertinent to note that these new skills when appropriately utilized will enhance academic performance of students and improve the image of the school but yet, school heads still deprive teachers from acquiring them because it tends to have accompanying demands of wage increase and extra motivation from management. Also, in most cases when teachers are allowed to pursue and improve on their skills, they are not adequately motivated in line with the new acquired skills which in essence tend to discourage and inhibit others from undertaking similar task; thus, the presence of modern day slavery in the teaching profession. In the view of Gilmore (2004), the following are some of the ways in modern day slavery manifests in the teaching profession:

- **Contract Slavery-** Where a worker is guaranteed employment, perhaps in a school, but when they arrive at their place of work they find themselves trapped and enslaved via the extra work load being given to them and the threat of sack and sanction. This pattern of slavery is common with an economically unstable country like Nigeria, where the chances of you getting another job is bleak.
- **Dehumanization-** To treat a person or group of people as a commodity, and less than human. Emphasis is placed here on the fact that teachers are made to do jobs outside the school duties and responsibilities. School head tends to engage teachers with responsibilities that goes against their terms of employment where such exist as it is rare, especially in private institutions of learning. In most cases tasks of this nature do not attract extra wages, hence teachers are made to work for free and outside one's will, which is a feature of slavery.
- **Discrimination** - To treat a person or group of people in a less favourable way on the basis of a particular characteristic or an aspect of their identity. Emphasis here in the school system is placed on a situation whereby the school head tends to malign a particular teacher because of his or her nature, qualification, sex, amongst others. Most times school heads take these action to victimize workers and display their authority, especially when teacher concerned are more qualified and exposed. Also, emphasis here is placed on edifying an ego of the school head with regards to controlling and managing teachers.
- **Exploitation** - A situation where one person labours for another under harsh and unhealthy conditions for very poor rates of pay as depicted in private and public school with the meager wages being paid and non-payment of salaries as at when due.

Methodology

The design for the investigation is the descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised teachers of public and private secondary schools in the state. The study randomly selected 318 participants, that is, 106 respondents from each senatorial district of the state. The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. The instrument was rated on a 4

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point likert scale of strongly agree =4, agree =3, disagree =2 and strongly disagree =1. Data generated was analyzed using mean ($\bar{x}$) and standard deviation statistics at a benchmark of mean ($\bar{x}$) of $p \leq 2.50$ as region for rejection and mean ($\bar{x}$) of $p \geq 2.50$ as region for acceptance of the research question.

Presentation of Results

Research Question

To what extent would adequate teacher education and professional development eliminate modern day slavery in the teaching profession? This question sought to find out how teacher education and their professional development will eradicate modern day slavery in the teaching profession in the state. Table 1 illustrate the views of respondents

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis onadequate and appropriate Teacher Education, Professional Development and Modern Day Slavery

S/n	Statement	No	Rating Scale				$\bar{x}$	St.D	Remark
			SA	A	D	SD			
1	Teacher education entails the policies and procedures designed to equip prospective teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom without any interferences and compulsion from school owners and authorities	318	460	213	194	96	3.0	1.7	Accepted
2	Teacher education as a programme relates to the development of teacher proficiency and competence that would enable and empower the teacher to meet the requirements of the profession and face the challenges therein with regards to modern day slavery	318	408	258	136	29	2.6	1.6	Accepted
3	Teacher education equips the teacher with the appropriate knowledge of the teaching profession that guides them against modern day slavery tenet from school authorities	318	492	123	120	64	2.5	1.5	Accepted
4	Effective professional development enables the classroom teacher to resist modern day slavery in the school system	318	452	225	132	20	2.6	1.6	Accepted
5	Teacher professional development equips the teacher to withstand institutional slavery in the profession	318	460	216	134	31	2.6	1.6	Accepted
6	Teacher professional development helps teachers to know when the act of slavery is being applied in the cause of their professional duties in the school	318	458	200	150	60	2.7	1.6	Accepted

Table 1 revealed that adequate and appropriate teacher education and teacher professional development equips the teacher to recognize when slavery tenet is about to and is being introduced in the teaching profession. This is reflected in the view of respondents on the 6 items that measure teacher education and teacher professional development and the implication of modern day slavery in the educational institution. Furthermore, results showed that all items was accepted as reflected in the mean score above the stated benchmark. Hence, the question that sought to measure teacher education and professional development was accepted. The implication here is that, with adequate teacher education and professional development, modern day slavery can be eradicated in the teaching profession across the state. This finding aligns with the studies carried out by Gilmore (2004), Kelvin (2004), ILO (2009), Sanyal (2013) and Chaurasia (2000) where they opined the relevance of teacher education and professional development, noting that teacher education and professional development equips the teacher to withstand outside pressure for them to indulge in duties outside their terms of employment. And that teacher education and professional development enhances teacher proficiency for efficiency and effectiveness in the teaching profession.

Conclusion

This paper is on teacher education, professional development and the implication of modern day slavery. It looks at the ways in which modern day slavery manifests in the teaching profession taking cognizance of the extra work load being given to teachers and sinister methods being used to retain teachers in the profession. In the light of all these, the paper concludes that adequate and appropriate teacher education and professional development place the teacher in a better position to identify and resist modern day slavery in the profession. Furthermore, the paper also noted that the institutionalization of slavery has a negative implication to the attainment of educational objectives.

Recommendations

Arising from the conclusion, the paper recommends that in the cause of training teachers, adequate and appropriate knowledge should be imbued in them so that they will recognize when slavery tenet in being applied to their duties and responsibilities as a teacher and also, teach them to appreciate their worth so that they cannot be easily threatened with sack and cowed into working against the terms of their employment.

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